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Finding Endometriosis using Machine Learning: FEMaLe

Introduction to Task 4.1 – Risk classifier

Polygenic risk scores (PRS) are popular and believed to be an important tool for precision medicine. A traditional PRS summarizes information about a person’s disease risk, based on numerous genetic variants (SNPs) in their genome. Each genetic variant confers a very little increase in disease risk, but when adding them up to a composite (or polygenic) risk score, it is possible to stratify people according to a distribution of risk for a disease. In other words, they can be used to assign people to different categories of risk based on their genetic makeup. The scores are useful for people in the extreme tails of risk distribution, but less useful for most people receiving an average risk score.

In our approach we will identify combinatorial risk scores (CRS), i.e., combinations of SNP genotypes that together exhibit a non-linear epistatic effect on phenotype. We count directly how many cases-control members have these combinatorial features and how strongly they are associated with their phenotype. This not only gives a more accurate score, but also a much more personalized one. We will also benchmark the combinatorial risk score to the traditional PRS to evaluate the added value of our approach for the risk classifier.

Partners in Task 4.1 are PrecisionLife (PREL), Aalborg University (AAU), and Oxford University (UOXF).

Development of platform for discovery, replication, and risk scoring

A major task of WP4 is to develop a platform for discovery and replication of specific combinations of SNP genotypes associated with endometriosis. The platform is important not just for the current Task 4.1, but also for the upcoming Task 4.2 (stratification of subgroups of patients with endometriosis), Task 4.3 (validation and refinement of endometriosis subtypes in independent cohorts) and Task 4.4 (clinical decision support tools, based on the signature of the individual patient).

In Task 4.1 we use a dataset from UK Biobank (UKBB) for discovery of genotype combinations associated with endometriosis and an independent dataset from Copenhagen Biobank (CHB) and Danish Blood Donor Studies (DBDS) for replication of the combinations and for testing the risk profiles of the individual samples. The major workflow is sketched in the figure below.

Figure 1. Overview of the Task 4.1 workflow.

The development process is based on interactive prototyping in close collaboration between the partners in WP4. PREL is responsible for the discovery process (using the patented MARKERS technology for combinatorial analytics), while the replication and risk scoring pipeline (AAU and UOXF) is independent of the discovery process in terms of software and data. Hence, we ensure the quality and independence of replication testing, while we also work on a shared data format for genotype combinations and case and controls definitions. This format is also prepared for clinical decision support (CDS) tools later in WP4.

Definition of endometriosis cases and controls in the UK Biobank

The discovery dataset is the UK Biobank (UKBB) comprised of 500k women and men aged 40-69 at the time of recruitment (2006-2010) from across the UK. In the UKBB, information was collected from participants during recruitment using questionnaires on socioeconomic status, lifestyle, family history and medical history. Participants were also followed up for cause-specific morbidity and mortality through linkage to disease registries, death registries, hospital admission records and primary care data.

Also, a range of biological samples including blood, urine and saliva were collected from the participants. A more detailed description of the UKBB can be found in the UK Biobank protocol (UK Biobank 2011). From this resource, we have pulled 3,562 self-report endometriosis cases of which 90% also reported a related surgery such as laparoscopy. Moreover, from medical records (International Classification of Diseases [ICD]; ICD9/ICD10) 4,110 endometriosis cases were defined. In total, 6,829 endometriosis cases had genotype data and of white British ancestry. These were further restricted to unrelated cases without adenomyosis, defined as endometriosis of the uterus which is a highly co-morbid diagnosis with endometriosis (N80.0), 4,875 endometriosis cases. For the controls, we have selected 68,167 random set of white British females without endometriosis or adenomyosis that is 10 times more than our case group to maximise statistical power.

Definition of endometriosis cases and controls in Danish datasets

The dataset used for replication is a combination of the Danish Blood Donor Study (DBDS; dbds.dk)¹ and the Copenhagen Hospital Biobank². The DBDS is a large prospective cohort of blood donors aiming at identifying predictors of healthy donors and as part of this cohort the DBDS Genomic Cohort have assessed SNPs among 110,000 donors for large-scale genetic analyses. CHB is a cohort of more than 400,000 genotyped individuals, which takes advantage of existing infrastructure at the Blood Banking facilities in the Capital Region of Denmark and is based on leftover EDTA whole blood from samples drawn for blood type testing or red cell antibody screening. All individuals in the two biobanks are linked to Danish registers using the Civil Registration System number, which is a 10-digit personal identification number unique for all Danish residents. To define cases and controls, we used ICD8 and ICD10.

The hospital records (ICD8 and ICD10 codes) were used to define endometriosis cases from CHB and DBDS. Individuals with adenomyosis diagnoses (ICD10 N80.0 or ICD8 62531) but no endometriosis diagnosis were excluded from the case set. In total, 4,165 cases and 48,841 female controls without known diagnosis of endometriosis or adenomyosis were included in the analysis.

The general workflow of identification and testing of genotypes combinations is the following:

1. **Pre-filtering** – preparation of the specific dataset to be analyzed, which can include:
 - removal of SNPs that are in linkage disequilibrium (LD) using for example LD clumping (not used on the current dataset from UKBB).
 - removal of SNPs and/or other features that are irrelevant to or not likely to be of sufficient statistical significance for the analysis, for example those where the major:minor allele frequencies are such that there are insufficient examples to ever meet the minimum case number requirements of our method.
 - selection (inclusion) of specific SNPs and features (usually hypothesis driven).
2. **Mining** – find all n-states of SNP genotypes with high-risk ratios found in many cases and a few controls.
3. **Permutations** – repeat mining on 1,000 random permutations of all samples keeping the case:control ratio and all parameters from mining.
4. **Test for significance** – determine the p-value of each n-state by counting the number of permutations with at least the number of cases and the risk ratio of the given n-state. Thus, we use minimum case prevalence and minimum risk ratio as the null hypothesis.
5. **FDR filtering** – the p-values are filtered by the Benjamini-Hochberg procedure.

Figure 3 (below) is an example of output after FDR filtering with some significant combinations of 2 SNP genotypes (2-states). The field “N-state_names” represents the specific 2-state, where the SNP rs-number is followed by either of the genotypes 0,1 or 2:

- 0: homozygote of the major allele
- 1: heterozygote
- 2: homozygote of the minor allele

For example, the first combination has the interpretation: (rs12082399=2) and (rs78473865=1). The combination is found in 129 cases and 931 controls, and the associated risk ratio is 1.937. The field ‘p1000=0’ means that 0 permutations out of 1000 yield at least one 2-state with at least 129 cases and a risk ratio greater than 1.967. The p-value is thus less than 0.001.

layer	N-state	N-state_names	#cases	#controls	risk_ratio	p1000
2	((1768 2)(2...	(rs12082399 2)(rs78473865 1)	129	931	1.937	0
2	((3100 1)(3...	(rs2959261 1)(rs136029 2)	353	3481	1.418	0
2	((25194 0)(...	(rs4486849 0)(rs5883 1)	474	4822	1.375	0
2	((13069 0)(...	(rs6557210 0)(rs1978344 2)	490	5125	1.337	0
2	((324 1)(14...	(rs12038474 1)(rs35446630 1)	491	5143	1.335	0
2	((322 1)(10...	(rs61778046 1)(rs30386 1)	826	8996	1.284	0
2	((324 1)(10...	(rs12038474 1)(rs30386 1)	858	9431	1.272	0
2	((324 1)(25...	(rs12038474 1)(rs8024196 1)	713	7854	1.269	0
2	((324 1)(11...	(rs12038474 1)(rs9349212 0)	698	7704	1.267	0
2	((324 1)(16...	(rs12038474 1)(rs7848864 1)	765	8494	1.259	0
2	((324 1)(16...	(rs12038474 1)(rs7844999 1)	812	9110	1.246	0
2	((13067 1)(...	(rs11751190 1)(rs1914157 1)	913	10259	1.244	0
2	((326 0)(16...	(rs2744701 0)(rs17728284 0)	949	10831	1.225	0
2	((13069 0)(...	(rs6557210 0)(rs9524525 0)	947	10829	1.223	0
2	((7695 1)(1...	(Affx-24552785 1)(rs2474881 1)	308	2927	1.471	1
2	((711 1)(41...	(rs6661505 1)(rs62178493 1)	434	4441	1.366	1
2	((1927 1)(1...	(rs12750834 1)(rs803407 1)	542	5706	1.328	1
2	((1066 1)(1...	(rs11165277 1)(rs6557210 0)	622	6738	1.291	1

Figure 3. Example of output with combinations from layer 2.

In general, high-order combinations are associated with low case prevalence and high-risk ratio, while low-order combinations may be found in many cases, but with a relatively small risk ratio. Figure 4 shows significant 5-states from the same output file used in Figure 3. An important subtask of the platform development is therefore to test the replication quality of low-order versus high-order combinations.

layer	N-state	N-state_names	#cases	#controls	risk_rat...	p1000
5	((843 1)(...	(rs72685833 1)(rs6854816 1)(rs7989894 0)(rs1743040 2)(rs7224327 0)	34	37	12.85	0
5	((5205 0...	(rs11720652 0)(rs116979936 1)(rs10743192 0)(rs17239770 1)(rs4458100 1)	46	97	6.631	1
5	((6056 1...	(rs6438025 1)(rs7933586 1)(rs9509690 2)(rs8058755 0)(rs12939483 0)	46	98	6.563	1
5	((15884 ...	(rs10107891 0)(rs9297669 1)(rs3760627 1)(rs113570942 1)(rs374015 1)	48	103	6.516	0
5	((4781 1...	(rs34991331 1)(rs16912559 0)(rs7178777 0)(rs4781070 0)(rs2436461 0)	48	104	6.454	2
5	((4781 1...	(rs34991331 1)(rs16912559 0)(rs7178634 0)(rs4781070 0)(rs2436461 0)	48	105	6.392	2
4	((1078 1...	(rs3903882 1)(rs2363517 0)(rs58210769 2)(rs12778234 1)	43	95	6.329	0
5	((8089 0...	(rs1859156 0)(rs7016153 0)(rs13250989 1)(rs11789520 2)(rs222121 1)	52	120	6.059	0
4	((6056 1...	(rs6438025 1)(rs7933586 1)(rs9509690 2)(rs8058755 0)	48	118	5.688	0
5	((5518 1...	(rs73065816 1)(rs548692 1)(rs10242061 1)(rs705350 1)(rs11068016 1)	55	145	5.304	2
5	((4097 1...	(rs62178493 1)(rs10804923 0)(rs4495161 2)(rs4294009 0)(rs41271807 0)	60	167	5.024	0
5	((3102 0...	(rs17033490 0)(rs11984461 0)(rs13250989 1)(rs11789520 2)(rs222121 1)	59	165	5	2
5	((4835 0...	(rs11674242 0)(rs7016153 0)(rs13250989 1)(rs11789520 2)(rs222121 1)	59	166	4.97	2
5	((3063 0...	(Affx-20082067 0)(rs7571513 0)(rs6451303 0)(rs77756209 1)(rs34109424 1)	58	164	4.945	2
5	((3102 0...	(rs17033490 0)(rs7016153 0)(rs13250989 1)(rs11789520 2)(rs222121 1)	64	181	4.944	0
5	((8047 1...	(rs7685009 1)(rs800708 0)(rs11772804 0)(rs17499386 0)(rs9583607 2)	59	167	4.94	2

Figure 4. Example of output with combinations from layer 5.

Format for sharing of the high-risk genotype combinations for replication

To test the genomic signature and risk profile of any patient, all possible genotype combinations must be taken into account. We therefore use the ‘expanded’ representation with all genotype combinations associated with given SNPs as input for the pipeline working on the Danish data. For example, the combination (rs12082399=2 and rs78473865=1) found in 129 cases and 931 controls is an output n-state as shown in Figure 3.

The table below shows all 9 possible genotype combinations of the two SNPs (ordered from 0,0 – 2,2) with the associated counts of cases and controls and the derived Z-scores and odds ratios. The field ‘reference’ is 1 for the specific output n-state generated by the MARKERS platform.

N-state_names	#cases	#controls	#total-cases	#total-controls	zScore	oddsratio	reference
(rs12082399 0)(rs78473865 0)	1763	25130	4782	66801	-103	0.9683	0
(rs12082399 0)(rs78473865 1)	276	3775	4782	66801	35	1.023	0
(rs12082399 0)(rs78473865 2)	4	145	4782	66801	-195	0.3848	0
(rs12082399 1)(rs78473865 0)	1851	25959	4782	66801	-20	0.9936	0
(rs12082399 1)(rs78473865 1)	262	3903	4782	66801	-103	0.9341	0
(rs12082399 1)(rs78473865 2)	7	157	4782	66801	-123	0.6223	0
(rs12082399 2)(rs78473865 0)	484	6763	4782	66801	0	0.9997	0
(rs12082399 2)(rs78473865 1)	129	931	4782	66801	722	1.962	1
(rs12082399 2)(rs78473865 2)	6	38	4782	66801	185	2.207	0

Figure 5. Expanded format with all 9 possible genotype combinations of 2 SNPs.

In general, an n-state of order n can be expanded into 3^n genotype combinations. For discovery and replication, we have tested n-states of orders 2-5, i.e., the numbers of expanded genotypes are in the range from 9 to 243.

Pipeline for replication of high-risk genotype combinations

A pipeline for testing the significant n-states discovered in UK Biobank within the Danish cohorts were established. The procedure involves the following steps:

1. Count the number of cases and controls in the Danish cohort with a specific high-risk genotype combination.
2. Compute odds ratio (OR) of the given n-state.
3. Obtain an empirical P-value by permutation test, in which cases-controls status were shuffled 1000 times and OR for the permuted data was computed. The P-value was defined as the number of empirical ORs that were larger than the observed OR.
4. P-values were corrected for multiple testing using Benjamini-Hochberg FDR.

Computation of risk scores for endometriosis

Polygenic risk scores (PRS)

PRS for endometriosis were calculated in DBDS-CHB using genome-wide association study (GWAS) summary statistics from the most recent endometriosis GWAS meta-analysis from the International Endometriosis Genomic Consortium (Rahmioglu et al., manuscript under revision for publication). The GWAS did not include any overlapping samples with CHB or DBDS. The PRS was computed using LDpred2³ with the auto model that automatically estimates the proportion of causal variants (π) and SNP heritability (h_{SNP}^2) from data.

Combinatorial risk score (CRS)

CRS were calculated as the total number of high-risk genotype-combinations that each individual carries (field 'reference' in expanded n-states). A score was calculated for each n -state (i.e., the number of SNPs in the high-risk genotype combination) and the scores of all n -states were summed to a CRS, following scaling to mean of zero and variance of one.

Evaluation of risk scores in CHB

The predictive abilities of PRS and CRS were compared by calculating area under the curve (AUC) for each risk score.

We furthermore modified a method for combining different genetic risk scores⁴, to combine the PRS and CRS for endometriosis. The resulting aggregated risk score (ARS) was calculated as:

$$ARS = \omega_i * PRS + (1 - \omega_i) * CRS$$

where the weight, ω_i , was determined by testing values between 0 and 1 in intervals of 0.01 and selecting the ω_i that gave the best discriminative ability.

Results

Discovery of significant high-risk genotype combinations for endometriosis in UK Biobank

The discovery of genotype combinations was conducted within the PrecisionLife MARKERS platform including 4,875 endometriosis cases, 68,167 female controls and 375,981 SNPs within the UKBB dataset. The parameters set within the platform were as following:

- minRiskRatio=1.2 (minimum risk ratio of each n-state).
- minCases=30 (minimum number of cases in each n-state).
- Combinations of order 2-5 were analyzed.
- Maximum number of combinations to be tested in each layer: 6 million.
- FDR = 2%.

The results are summarized in the table 1. In total, 1,298 significant SNP genotype combinations of orders 2-5 were identified. A total of 2,566 SNPs were utilized in the results with 100% penetrance in 4,875 cases.

State	Number of combinations (after mining)	Number of significant combinations with FDR = 2%	Risk ratio in each combination	Number of cases in each combination	Total number of cases	Total number of SNP genotypes
2	3,954,563	35	1.204 – 1.99	115-999	4,552	53
3	5,999,902	100	1.375 – 3.093	73 - 590	4,860	27
4	5,999,898	162	1.713 – 6.329	43 - 309	4,821	435
5	5,999,953	1,001	1.979 – 12.85	34 - 265	4,875	2051
All	21,954,316	1,298	1.204 – 12,85	34 - 999	4,875	2,566

Table 1. Overview of summary of significant genotype combination results for endometriosis from 2-5 states.

Note that layer 5 counts 1,001 combinations with 100% penetrance and just 2,051 unique SNP genotypes. Thus, some of these SNP genotypes are found in a number of combinations hence defining *networks* of combinations. The most frequent SNP genotypes found in 353-363 of the 1,001 combinations in layer 5 are:

rs12038474 = 1
rs35192091 = 1
rs7806462 = 0
rs1748365 = 2

Replication of high-risk genotype combinations for endometriosis in DBDS and CHB

An overview of how the high-risk genotype combinations replicated in the Danish cohort is shown in figure 6. Among the high-risk genotype combinations with 2, 3 and 4 SNP-genotypes, 4 of 35, 1 of 100 and 0 of 162 showed statistical replication, respectively. High-risk genotype combinations with 5 SNPs had a much higher replication rate with 299 of 1001 genotype combinations having significant odds ratios.

Figure 6. Replication of high-risk genotype combinations with two to five SNPs in the Danish cohort. The upper panels show the distribution of odds ratios in the Danish cohorts for the high-risk genotype combinations that were identified in the UKB cohort. The panel below shows the distribution of $-\log_{10} P$ -values derived from permutations and corrected for multiple testing, with an indication of how many combinations were significant.

Risk score for endometriosis

The polygenic risk scores (PRS) for endometriosis in DBDS and CHB was found to be significantly higher in cases compared to controls ($p = 1.95 \times 10^{-101}$).

Figure 7. Distribution plot of standardized polygenic risk scores (PRS) for endometriosis shown for cases and controls in the Danish cohort.

The accuracy of prediction of endometriosis in CHB/DBDS was AUC=0.61 for the additive PRS (Figure 7), whereas the accuracy for the non-linear effects of CRS was AUC=0.553 (Figure 8). Combining the PRS and CRS into the ARS the AUC increased to 0.615 at the optimum $\omega = 0.92$. Thus, combining the PRS and CRS increased the discriminative ability of the risk score by 0.5 percentage points (Figure 9).

Figure 8. Area under the curve (AUC) for genetic risk scores calculated in the Danish cohorts. CRS-2 through CRS-5 are state-specific combinatorial risk scores for high-risk genotype combinations with two through five SNPs, respectively, and CRS is the combinatorial risk score based on all five states. PRS+CRS is the sum of the polygenic risk score and the CRS, and ARS is the aggregated risk score that combines the additive effects of the PRS with the non-linear effects of the CRS.

Figure 9. Determination of the optimum weight ω that results in the highest AUC when combining polygenic risk scores (PRS) with the combinatorial risk scores (CRS) into an aggregated risk score (ARS).

Distinct genetic subtypes of endometriosis

We used the replicated, highly significant 5-state combinations ($n = 299$) to perform a genetic network analysis. In Figure 10, each node represents a specific SNP and an edge between two SNPs indicate that the two SNPs are represented in the same high-risk genotype combination. This clearly indicates that there are genetically distinct subtypes. Next step is to expand this genetic map to also include the lower-order genotype combinations, and to use it to identify patient subtypes using health registry data.

Figure 10. Genetic network analysis of replicated 5-state high-risk genotype combinations. Nodes indicate SNPs and edges indicate that SNPs exist in the same high-risk genotype combination.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we have built a pipeline that involves discovery of high-risk genotype combinations, replication of these genotype combinations and computation of risk scores for endometriosis. The risk score computation involves both the additive genetic risk scores (PRS) as well as combinatorial genetic risk scores (CRS) that are not additive and we benchmark and combine these scores to see if we can achieve better prediction of endometriosis. Final optimisations for the pipeline will be made to include the 42 genome-wide significant established endometriosis risk variants (IEGC Endometriosis GWAS manuscript under review) in the discovery of high-risk genotype combinations with an aim to improve the prediction (AUC) for endometriosis. Once the high-risk combinations are finalised, we are moving on to task 4.2 where these identified genetic sub-types of endometriosis will be defined utilising the densely phenotyped Danish datasets CHB and DBDS.

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